

To reproduce the figures presented in the manuscript, run the following MATLAB scripts:

- **PS_theo_simLang.m** reproduces **Fig. 2**.
- **figureSolLang_vs_det.m** reproduces **Fig. 1**.
- **peakPosition_vs_gamma.m** reproduces **Fig. 3**.
- **plotPowerSpectrumTheo_noise_only_z_v2.m** reproduces **Fig. 4**.

Auxiliary files

The following functions are required by the scripts above:

- **JacobianMatrix_only_z.m** computes the Jacobian matrix associated with Eq. (24).
- **power_spectrum_sim.m** computes the numerical power spectrum from stochastic realizations.
- **power_spectrum.m** computes the theoretical power spectrum given by Eq. (15).
- **powerSpectrum_noise_only_z_v2.m** computes the theoretical power spectrum given by Eq. (25).
- **sol_Det.m** numerically solves the deterministic system described by Eq. (6).
- **sol_Lang.m** numerically integrates the Langevin equation (10).